

D6.1. Product Design Specifications

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About ThrombUS+

Deep vein thrombosis (DVT) is the formation of a blood clot within the deep veins, most commonly those of the lower limbs, causing obstruction of blood flow. In 50% of people with DVT, the clot eventually breaks off and travels to the lung to cause pulmonary embolism. Clinical assessment of DVT is notoriously unreliable because up to 2/3 of DVT episodes are clinically silent and patients are symptom free even when pulmonary embolism has developed. Early diagnosis of DVT is crucial and despite the progress made in ultrasound imaging and plethysmography techniques, there is a need for new methods to enable continuous monitoring DVT diagnosis at the point of care.

ThrombUS+ brings together an interdisciplinary team of industrial, technology, regulatory, social science and clinical trial experts to develop a novel wearable diagnostic device for point-of-care, operator free, continuous monitoring in patients with high DVT risk. The device will combine autonomous, AI driven DVT detection based on a novel wearable ultrasound hardware, impedance plethysmography and light reflection rheography for immediate detection of blood clot formation in the lower limb. Activity and other physiological measurements will be used to provide a continuous assessment of DVT risk and support DVT prevention via serious gaming. The aggregated data will drive an intelligence decision support unit that will provide accurate monitoring and alerts. Extended reality will be used to guide experts to design exercises and patients to use the device optimally.

ThrombUS+ is intended for use by postoperative patients in the ward, during long surgical operations, cancer patients or otherwise bedridden patients at home or in care units, and women during pregnancy and postpartum. ThrombUS+ will use big data sets for AI training collected in the project via 3 large scale clinical studies and will validate the outcome in the clinical setting via 1 early feasibility study and 1 multi-center clinical trial.

Deliverable D6.1 Description

Task 6.1 aims at preparing a thorough review of relevant standards, quality guidelines of medical devices, and statutory regulations that ultimately need to be met by the finished product.

These will be used to establish critical product specifications, which in turn, will be used to devise a testing strategy to ascertain compliance with the predefined standards and specifications.

Key end-users requirements will be prioritized through a Quality-Function Deployment tool, and they will be translated to specifications, considering outcomes of WP2.

The task is led by KTU, an expert in sensor and sensor technology hardware and software, thus ensuring an extended expertise to overview the technical integration of the ThrombUS+ solution. The regulatory partner VDE has a crucial role in ensuring that compliance by design aspects are defined. All partners participate to ensure continuity with the rest of the project activities.

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Terms and Definitions

Abbreviation	Definition
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIA	Artificial Intelligence Act
API	Application Programming Interface
AUC	Area Under Curve
CDUS	Compression Duplex Ultrasound
CHI	Identifier for ThrombUS+ Central Hub & Intelligence Module
CNN	Convolutional Neural Network
CSW	C-shell type Semirigid Wearable
CUS	Compression Ultrasound Imaging
DICOM	Digital Imaging and Communications in Medicine
DoA	Description of Action
DVT	Deep Vein Thrombosis
EAC	Identifier for ThrombUS+ Electronic Actuator Controller
EC	European Commission
EIM	Identifier for ThrombUS+ Electrical Impedance Module
EIP	Electrical Impedance Plethysmography
EU	European Union
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HADEA	European Health and Digital Executive Agency
IMU	Inertial Measurement Unit
IoU	Intersection over Union
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
LAM	Identifier for ThrombUS+ Limb Activity Module
LRM	Identifier for ThrombUS+ Light Rheography Module
LRR	Light Reflection Rheography
MEMS	Micro-Electro-Mechanical System
MDR	Medical Device Regulation
ML	Machine Learning
npm	Node Package Manager
PPG	Photoplethysmography
PZT	Pb (ZrTi) - shorten form of Lead zirconate titanate

ReLU	Rectified Linear Unit
ROC	Receiver-Operating Characteristic
RUCs	Reference Use Cases
SDK	Software Development Kit
UI	User Interface
US	Ultrasound
USM	Identifier for ThrombUS+ Ultrasound Monitoring Module
VOP	Venous Occlusion Plethysmography
WAM	Identifier for ThrombUS+ Wearable Actuator Module
WI-Fi	Wireless Fidelity
WP	Work Package
WSN	Identifier for ThrombUS+ Wearable Sensors Network
WTC	Identifier for ThrombUS+ Wearable Thigh Cuff
WTE	Identifier for ThrombUS+ Wearable Tetrapolar Electrode
WUSD	Identifier for ThrombUS+ Wearable Ultrasound Device
XGM	Identifier for ThrombUS+ Extended Reality and Serious Gaming Module
XR	Extended Reality

Executive Summary

Deliverable D6.1 aims to revise the high-level regulatory, technical, and functional requirements outlined in previous deliverables (D2.2, D2.3, and D2.4) and provide detailed specifications for the ThrombUS+ system, designed for monitoring and preventing deep vein thrombosis (DVT).

A thorough analysis of the proposed conceptual architecture revealed the need for two critical external components: a dedicated Wi-Fi router for secure, reliable, and low-latency communication between modules, independent of the hospital network, and an isolating power transformer to ensure electrical safety, noise reduction, and compliance with medical standards. These additions were incorporated into the system design. The internal ThrombUS+ system modules were categorized into hardware and software components, with detailed specifications provided in standardized tables. This process involved making several key decisions, and the specifications will serve as a foundation for the development of individual modules and subsystems in the future.

The ThrombUS+ system is designed with high modularity, allowing flexible configuration and integration of different modules to support various DVT monitoring methods. The primary monitoring methods include compression duplex ultrasonography, venous occlusion plethysmography, and light reflection rheography. Each method will utilize different module sets and operate in one of three working modes: imaging, monitoring, or analysis. A separate set of modules will also focus on DVT prevention.

Finally, the deliverable identifies potential improvements to the ThrombUS+ system development process, including the adoption of embedded systems design methodologies, optimization of real-time embedded execution, risk mitigation strategies, and the possibility of extending the system to support telemonitoring.

1. Introduction

ThrombUS+ product design specification is based on the WHO recommendations, developed with the help of experts, on technical specifications for 61 medical devices for healthcare facilities¹. The structure of technical specifications approach was taken as a template for deliverable. The internal ThrombUS+ system modules were divided into hardware and software components, with specifications outlined in standardized tables. This process requires making several important decisions, and the resulting specifications will serve as a basis for the future development of individual modules and subsystems.

The findings presented in this report aim to support the integration, validation, and testing methodology for ThrombUS+ (T6.2), as well as the integration of the overall system (T6.3–T6.5). Additionally, these results contribute to the development of automatic DVT monitoring software in WP6.

While the previous report on technical and functional requirements outlined the necessary components for ThrombUS+ system operation, this product design specification report focuses on the system's offerings. Specifically, it highlights the actual capabilities and features of the system, providing a detailed description to enable users and professionals to evaluate and compare it with similar systems.

Furthermore, the report serves as a planning document for testing and verifying ThrombUS+ against the system requirements defined by standards and device specifications. These specifications detail the system's capabilities and its compliance with regulatory standards. While the core requirements and critical specifications are structured around user needs, this document does not provide an exhaustive discussion of the detailed requirements for each ThrombUS+ module, as these are thoroughly addressed in D2.3.

This specification approach ensures that the device is safe, effective, and reliable for its intended use.

2. Background

2.1. Intended purpose of ThrombUS+ device

ThrombUS+ is an active wearable diagnostic device for point-of-care, continuous (intermittent) monitoring in patients with increased risk for deep vein thrombosis (DVT), that is applied to the patient's lower limb. For this purpose, ThrombUS+ autonomously combines compression ultrasound imaging (CUS), electrical impedance plethysmography (EIP), and light reflection rheography (LRR) to assess blood clot formation and blood flow on the lower limbs.

Additionally, ThrombUS+ uses inertial measurement units (IMUs) to monitor patient's lower limb activity. Via an extended reality (XR) environment and serious gaming, patients are trained and motivated, respectively, to perform lower limb exercises for DVT prevention at the point-of-care.

ThrombUS+ is intended for application to adult patients in the clinical environment by healthcare professionals.

2.2. Use cases and main user requirements

In the deliverable D2.1, patient centric Reference Use Cases (RUC) were defined and analyzed:

- RUC#1 Neurosurgery
- RUC#2 Lower limb orthopedic surgery
- RUC#3 Cardiovascular surgery

¹ WHO technical specifications for 61 medical devices, <https://www.who.int/publications/m/item/who-technical-specifications-for-61-medical-devices>

- RUC#4 Pregnancy and postpartum
- RUC#5 Obesity
- RUC#6 Cancer and oncological treatment
- RUC#7 Autoimmune diseases and genetic disorders

In D2.1, a comprehensive description of each RUC has been presented, including risk factors and clinical background, patient and monitoring process needs, the ThrombUS+ added value, and high-level acceptability and design requirements. This information serves as a foundation for the subsequent aggregation and definition of users and their main requirements, as well as for outlining the key ThrombUS+ functionalities, which require further analysis of related standards and regulations. Considering the 'Intended Purpose of the ThrombUS+ Device', which states that 'ThrombUS+ is intended for application to adult patients in a clinical environment by healthcare professionals', the decision was made to focus on the first three RUCs, which are related to post-surgery DVT monitoring. However, the other RUCs can still be taken into account by the ThrombUS+ subsystems.

Users of the ThrombUS+ system can be categorized as follows (D2.3):

- Medical specialists: doctor, physical therapist, nurse, medical technician.
- Administrators: system administrator, maintenance engineers.
- Researchers: medical researcher, biomedical engineer.

Patients are not listed as users of the ThrombUS+ system because they are the subjects or recipients of the monitoring, rather than the active participants in operating the system. In this context, the term "user" refers to individuals who interact directly with the system for the purpose of managing or analyzing the data, i.e., healthcare professionals: doctors, nurses, therapists, or technicians who monitor and interpret the data provided by the system.

2.3. General architecture of ThrombUS+ system

The modular structure of the ThrombUS+ system, along with internal relationships, was introduced in the deliverable D2.3, elaborated in D2.4 and even further elaborated in this report, see Figure 1.

Figure 1. Conceptual modules and their interrelationships in the ThrombUS+ system.

The internal ThrombUS+ modules, such as the CHI, comprise hardware (a laptop) and software (ThrombUS+ applications) that controls actuators, collects and processes sensor data, and implements both operator-controlled and independent DVT monitoring methods. It also facilitates patient guidance and decision support. The WAM compresses thigh tissue to enable Compression Duplex Ultrasonography (CDUS), automatic ultrasound transducer steering for operator-independent monitoring, and Venous Occlusion Plethysmography (VOP) using the EIM and LRM modules. The USM performs intermittent, operator-independent DVT monitoring through ultrasound imaging and deep vein segmentation, thrombus detection via vein localization and dimensional tracking, blood flow perturbation estimation using Color, Power, and Wave Doppler imaging, and continuous data streaming for DVT risk assessment and thrombus characterization. The EIM and LRM support the VOP method, with the LRM also facilitating the tiptoe DVT test. The LAM enables a serious game for DVT prophylaxis and provides biofeedback on lower limb movements during ultrasound monitoring. Finally, the XGM is a software module for DVT risk estimation and prevention.

In addition to the internal modules, the ThrombUS+ system requires two external non-medical modules: a Wi-Fi router and an isolating power transformer. The Wi-Fi Router is needed for establishing a local wireless network among LRM, EIM and LAM modules, and CHI. Establishing a local wireless network between modules is preferable to connecting each module to the hospital network due to reliability, security, low latency, independence, and ease of integration. A dedicated local network ensures stable and consistent communication without relying on hospital network availability, which may be subject to congestion or restrictions. It also enhances security by reducing exposure to cybersecurity threats and unauthorized access. In addition, direct communication between modules minimizes data transmission delays, which is important for real-time monitoring. The system remains functional even during hospital network outages, ensuring uninterrupted operation. Furthermore, a local network avoids compatibility issues with hospital IT infrastructure and reduces administrative overhead related to network configuration and security policies.

An isolating transformer for power supply to the ThrombUS+ system is essential in the hospital for several reasons. It ensures electrical safety by providing galvanic isolation between the system and the hospital's power grid, protecting patients and operators from electrical shocks. The transformer also aids in noise reduction, filtering out electrical interference from other hospital equipment. In addition, it prevents ground loops by eliminating differences in electrical potential between grounded equipment, thus avoiding erratic behavior or signal distortion. Finally, the use of an isolating transformer ensures regulatory compliance, meeting strict electrical safety standards for medical devices and enhancing overall patient and staff safety.

2.4. Compliance and standards

The ThrombUS+ system must comply with various standards, guidelines, and legislation. In deliverable D2.2. "Regulatory framework, security, safety and ethics strategy, and guidelines" (submitted on 17 July 2024) the respective requirements have been summarized. Essentially, the ThrombUS+ system underlies the provisions of Regulation (EU) 2017/745 (Medical Devices Regulation, MDR) and Regulation (EU) 2024/1689 (Artificial Intelligence Act, AI Act)² for access to the EU market. Moreover, other EU legislation as the Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (General Data Protection Regulation, GDPR) is applicable as well. Important standards to apply for MDR compliance include EN ISO 13485 (quality management), EN 60601-1 (safety), EN 62304 (software life cycle processes), EN ISO 14971 (risk management) and EN 62366-1 (usability). In addition, the guidelines of the Medical Device Coordination Group (MDCG) must be considered, for example with regard to clinical evaluation and post-market surveillance.

² Regulation (EU) 2024/1689 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 June 2024 laying down harmonised rules on artificial intelligence and amending Regulations (EC) No 300/2008, (EU) No 167/2013, (EU) No 168/2013, (EU) 2018/858, (EU) 2018/1139 and (EU) 2019/2144 and Directives 2014/90/EU, (EU) 2016/797 and (EU) 2020/1828 (Artificial Intelligence Act)

In order to identify the applicable General Safety and Performance Requirements of Annex I MDR (cf. 3.3.1.3-PR01 List of applicable General Safety and Performance Requirements (GSPR)), a risk characterization was performed and will be updated, when and if necessary. As certain ThrombUS+ system parts involve artificial intelligence, applicable requirements in the European AI Act and the “Questionnaire: Artificial Intelligence in Medical Devices”³ were identified (cf. 3.3.1.9-PR01 Requirements for medical devices as high-risk AI systems and 3.3.1.7-PR01 Requirement list AI-model development, respectively). As standards for use under the AI Act are still being developed, few are currently available. Examples are BS/AAMI 34971 (risk management) and ISO/IEC 5259 series (Data management).

Insights from WP6 and other work packages are considered to set up technical documentation as requested by MDR and AI Act with the following structure:

- Product description and specification.
- Information to be supplied by the manufacturer.
- Design and manufacturing information.
- Safety and performance requirements.
- Risk-benefit analysis and risk management.
- Product verification and validation.
- Post-market surveillance and vigilance.

For example, the technical documentation includes an evolving list of system requirements for all ThrombUS+ modules, which forms the basis of the technical specifications in Chapter 3.

3. Technical specifications of the ThrombUS+ modules

3.1. Central Hub & Intelligence (CHI)

3.1.1. Hardware

The hardware specifications and the minimal requirements for the Central Hub and Intelligence Module (CHI) are provided in Table 1.

Table 1. Hardware specifications of the CHI module.

General information	
Generic name	Central Hub & Intelligence Module (CHI)
Type	Hardware
Version	Latest released version
Author	Off-the-shelf
Technical characteristics	
Hardware Acceleration	Support for CUDA
RAM memory	At least 32GB

³ Questionnaire: Artificial Intelligence in Medical Devices (Ver. 1.1).” IG-NB and Team NB, 2024

ROM memory and disk	At least SDD 1TB
CPU	At least i7-14700HX
Display	At least 17 inches
Power supply	At least 6 cells
Accessories, consumables, spare parts, and other components	
Router for local Wi-Fi network	Support for mDNS
Power supply isolation	Isolating transformer IMEDe 150 VA (Noratel, Hokksund, Norway) or similar
Maintenance	
Maintenance tasks	<p>The hardware of the CHI module must always be kept in safe and reliable working order and should be checked regularly, at least once a year by the manufacturer or an authorized personnel. The check covers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – inspection for potential mechanical and functional damage, – readability and integrity of safety labels, – functional test of the device.

3.1.2. Software

These software specifications presented in Table 2 ensure the CHI module can properly execute, communicate with hardware (USB/sensors), and manage local data. The overall software architecture of CHI is summarized in Figure 2. Briefly, the main ThrombUS+ application is composed of a Service Manager that runs on the backend and handles the various services (i.e. SDKs and Core Services) and a Graphical User Interface (GUI) from which users can access the various functionalities and interact with the ThrombUS+ application. The SDK services manage the communication with the rest ThrombUS+ modules (i.e. sensors) by accessing their SDK libraries. The Service Manager also handles the Core Services which are necessary for the smooth operation of the main application and the entire ThrombUS+ system. These services include, but not limited to, the *LoggingService*, which handles the logging procedures, the *MLRunTimeService*, which handles the inference of various machine learning models that will be used within the ThrombUS+ device and the *DatabaseService*, which manages the interaction between the rest core services with the local *database*.

Table 2. Software-related specifications of the CHI module.

General information	
Operating System	Windows 11 or higher (64-bit)
Supported runtimes and drivers	Support the latest .NET runtime and provide standard USB/hardware drivers
Version	Latest released version
Author	ATHENA
Software requirements	
Runtime environment for running the main C# application	.NET 8 Runtime
Redistributable	Visual C++
Embedded database engine	SQLite for lightweight local data storage
Runtime: For web-based UI components	Microsoft Edge WebView2 Runtime installed by Evergreen Bootstrapper: A small installer that downloads and installs the latest runtime from Microsoft. WebView2 requires Windows 7 or later and is based on Microsoft Edge (Chromium) but does not need to match the installed Edge browser version.

Functional scope	
Data Handling	Import and store patient data: demographics, medical records, sensor streams.
	Manage local records until explicit clearance.
	Perform ML-based DVT risk analysis with TensorFlow.NET.
User Interfaces	Clinician Mode: Advanced control panels, device configuration, manual override.
	Patient Mode: Guided exercises, restricted controls, PIN-locked interface.
Security & Compliance	Mandatory PIN protection for lock/unlock states.
	Automatic logging of user actions (audit trail). Local data storage (SQLite) with no external transmission unless authorized.
Integration	REST endpoints for control/configuration.
	WebSocket for real-time communication (alerts, updates).
	UDP for high-frequency sensor data (IMU, external devices).
	Optional Unity-based extended reality features.
CHI software architecture	
Frontend	Windows Forms for core UI elements.
	Embedded WebView2 (Vue 3) for modern web-based components.
	Unity integration for XR scenarios (if required by the clinical setting).
Backend	C# (.NET 8) runtime managing data flow and core logic.
	SQLite database for persistent local storage.
	TensorFlow.NET library for DVT risk detection.
Communication protocols	REST API for device and application-level commands.
	WebSocket for low-latency streaming of alerts/ data visualization.
	UDP for raw sensor packet reception.
	IPC on Windows for local inter-process messaging.

Figure 2. The Central Hub & Intelligence software architecture. The main application consists of a Service Manager, which runs on the system’s tray and a graphical user interface (GUI) for interacting with the application’s functionality.

The various components of the database, their description and their relations are presented in Table 3 and a graphical representation of the database schema is presented in Figure 3. The fields for each database table, the data type of each field and the relationships between the different database tables are also represented in Figure 3.

Table 3. Database schema.

Table	Description	Relations
Games	Stores game configurations linked to exercises (title, difficulty, description, data)	FK Exerciseld → Exercises(Id) UNIQUE on (Exerciseld)
SensorData	Captures sensor outputs for each patient (type, timestamp, binary/string/JSON data)	FK PatientId → Patients(Id) UNIQUE on (PatientId)
RiskProfiles	Holds DVT-related risk factors and details for each patient	FK PatientId → Patients(Id) UNIQUE on (PatientId)
MaintenanceLog	Logs maintenance or calibration events (sensor type, version, notes).	None
Sessions	Session records (start/end times, type, data) per patient, specifying a source (exercise, game, exam).	FK PatientId → Patients(Id) UNIQUE on (PatientId) Column Source references domain (e.g., Exercise, Game, Exam)
Settings	System-wide or device-specific configuration entries (key-value pairs).	None
LogFiles	Logs user actions (timestamp, action, details) for auditing and compliance.	None
Notifications	Issues alerts per patient (severity, message, timestamps), referencing other entities.	FK PatientId (linked to Patients(Id) though it's also marked as a primary key in the schema)
Patients	Core patient records (names, DOB, health record).	FK to Notifications(PatientId) as per schema definition
PatientPlan	Encapsulates a patient's therapy plan, linking them to exercises and games (data, timestamp).	FK PatientId → Patients(Id) FK Exercises → Exercises(Id) FK Games → Games(Id) UNIQUE on (PatientId)
Exercises	Definitions of activities (description, media data, metadata).	Referenced by Games(Exerciseld) and PatientPlan(Exercises)

Figure 3. The ThrombUS+ database tables, with their respective fields and their data types, used within the Central Hub & Intelligence module.

Table 4 presents the CHI software frontend Node Package Manager (npm)⁴ dependencies. Node Package Manager is a dependency management tool for JavaScript, simplifying the installation, updating, and distribution of libraries to ensure version control and maintainability. It supports both open-source and private packages, contributed by a vast developer community.

Table 4. Software Node Package Manager dependencies of the Central Hub & Intelligence module.

npm Package Name	Version	Description
@quasar/extras	^1.16.4	Provides icon libraries and additional styles used by Quasar.
axios	^1.2.1	A promise-based HTTP client for making requests from browsers and Node.js.
d3	^7.9.0	A JavaScript library for producing dynamic, interactive data visualizations in web browsers.

⁴ Node Package Manager www.npmjs.com

d3-sankey	^0.12.3	A plugin for D3 that simplifies the creation of Sankey diagrams.
pinia	^2.0.11	An intuitive, lightweight store library for Vue 3, serving as an alternative to Vuex.
quasar	^2.16.0	A high-performance Vue.js framework for building rich, responsive UIs with Material Design.
vue	^3.4.18	The core progressive JavaScript framework for building user interfaces.
vue-i18n	^9.0.0	Internationalization plugin for Vue, enabling multi-language support.
vue-router	^4.0.0	The official router for Vue, managing navigation and route matching in single-page apps.

Table 5 presents the list of NuGet packages⁵ and their corresponding versions. NuGet Package Manager is a dependency management tool for .NET, streamlining the installation, updating, and distribution of libraries to ensure version control and maintainability. All referenced packages are open source with many contributors.

To connect, communicate, control, and collect data from the various sensors of the ThrombUS+ system, custom SDK libraries will be utilized. Table 6 presents the list of SDK embedded libraries under development for the ThrombUS+ system.

For the assessment of the ultrasound images two convolutional neural network (CNN) models tailored for real-time ultrasound image analysis will be developed and deployed within the Central Hub & Intelligence module. The first model, based on MobileNet architecture, is designed for multi-class classification, grading target veins using clinically relevant ultrasound DICOM frames as input. The second model, leveraging a U-Net architecture, performs pixel-wise classification to segment and label vascular structures. Both models receive preprocessed B-mode ultrasound images, where cropping, pixel normalization, resizing, and any additional adjustments are applied beforehand to ensure optimal input quality and alignment with the project's goals and objectives. The MobileNet-based classifier employs Leaky ReLU activation, optimizing performance with Cross Entropy or Focal Loss, while the U-Net segmentation model uses Dice Loss, JS divergence (Jensen-Shannon divergence), or KL divergence (Kullback–Leible divergence) for accurate mask generation. Evaluation metrics include Top-K and Balanced Accuracy for classification and Intersection over Union (IoU) and receiver-operating characteristic curve (ROC) and area under the curve (AUC) for segmentation. The models are trained in PyTorch and exported in .tflite format, ensuring compatibility with a real-time deployment pipeline in C# via TensorFlow.NET. Targeting an inference latency of under 30ms, this implementation supports efficient and accurate real-time vascular analysis for clinical applications. The specification of the SDK for DVT detections based on ultrasound images are listed below in Table 7.

Table 5. The list of NuGet packages and the version used within the ThrombUS+ Central Hub & Intelligence module.

NuGet Package Name	Version
TensorFlow.NET	0.150.0
AForge.Video	2.2.5
AForge.Video.DirectShow	2.2.5
Microsoft.EntityFrameworkCore	9.0.0
Microsoft.EntityFrameworkCore.Design	9.0.0
Microsoft.EntityFrameworkCore.Sqlite	9.0.0

⁵ NuGet packages www.nuget.org

Microsoft.Extensions.Configuration	9.0.0
Microsoft.Web.WebView2	1.0.2903.40
Swashbuckle.AspNetCore	7.2.0
System.Management	9.0.1
System.Net.Security	4.3.2
System.Net.WebSockets.Client	4.3.2
Microsoft.Extensions.Hosting	9.0.0
Zeroconf	3.7.16

Table 6. The list of the ThrombUS+ SDK embedded libraries.

Module	SDK embedded libraries
Ultrasound Module Telemed_SDK	Libs\Interop.Usgfw2Lib.dll
Limb Activity Module LAM_SDK	Libs\LAM_SDK.dll
Light Reflection Module LRM_SDK	Libs\LRM_SDK.dll
Electrical Impedance Module EIM_SDK	Libs\EIM_SDK.dll
Wearable Actuator Module WAM_SDK	Libs\WAM_SDK.dll

Table 7. The specification of SDK for DVT AI detection module.

General information	
Model Type	CNN MobileNet Based (Real-time Image Grading of Target Veins) CNN U-Net Based (Real-time Labelling of Vascular Structures)
Model Format	.tflite
Trained On	Ultrasound DICOM frames with clinically relevant information (.dcm files) and corresponding labels/annotations saved in .json format
Technical characteristics	
Input shape/format	[1, 1, 128, 128]
Model output	Multi-Class Classification (5 classes) - Probability (0-1) (Real-time Image Grading of Target Veins) Segmentation Masks – Pixel level classification with probability (0-1) (Real-time Labelling of Vascular Structures)
Activation Function	Leaky ReLU (Real-time Image Grading of Target Veins) Leaky ReLU (Real-time Labelling of Vascular Structures)
Loss Function	Cross Entropy Loss OR Focal Loss (Real-time Image Grading of Target Veins) Dice Loss OR JS div loss OR KL div loss (Real-time Labelling of Vascular Structures)
Evaluation Metrics	Top-K accuracy and balanced accuracy (real-time image grading of target veins)
Preprocessing	B-mode US area cropping, pixel array scaling [0,1], color-space correction if needed, input frame resizing to input shape, augmentations if needed, etc.)
Deployment	C# via TensorFlow.NET
Latency Target	< 30ms per frame for real-time analysis

3.2. Ultrasound Monitoring Module (USM)

3.2.1. Hardware

Table 8, Table 9, Table 10, and Table 11 present the specifications of the USM integrating together ultrasound beamformer and ultrasound transducers developed by TELEMED, VERMON, and FRAUNHOFER and software developed by ATHENA, respectively.

Table 8. Specifications of the ultrasound beamformer by TELEMED.

General information	
Generic name	Ultrasound Imaging System (ArtUs Compact Beamformer)
Type	Hardware and software
Version	<i>Latest released version</i>
Author	TELEMED
Technical characteristics	
Imaging modes	B-mode (bidimensional, simultaneous)
	M-mode
	Color Doppler
	Pulsed Doppler
	Harmonic Imaging
Depth of imaging	40 - 80 mm
Width of imaging	50 - 100 %
Receiver's gain range	0-100%
Emission power range	-20 to 0 dB
Dynamic range	36 - 102 dB
Frequency range	1-15 MHz
Focal depth	Up to 50 mm
Time - gain control	Adjustable in range 0-100% individually in each of five depth zones
Image memory	Frame by frame or cine-loop
Streaming data to CHI	USB 3.2, physical layer USB C.
Triggering Electronic Actuation Controller (EAC)	BNC connection, two ports IN and OUT
Memory capacity	Recording up to 1024 frames (PC memory dependent)
Power supply	External AC~220 V \pm 10% 50 Hz or DC +5V 500mA power from USB-C interface from the CHI module.
Environmental requirements	
Transport and storage conditions	Temperature: 10 to 40 °C
	Relative humidity: 15 to 85 % (non-condensing)
	Atmospheric pressure: 700 hPa to 1060 hPa
	Temperature: 10 to 40 °C

Operating and storage conditions	Relative humidity: 15 to 85 % (non-condensing)
	Atmospheric pressure: 700 hPa to 1060 hPa
Physical and chemical characteristics	
Physical components	Beamformer with socket connector for coaxial cables (multi-line) to imaging transducer and two SMA Jack sockets for IN and OUT triggers; USB cable with both endings USB-C; external module for power supply +5V.
	USB cable with both endings USB-C
	external module for power supply +5V.
Raw materials	N/A
Accessories, consumables, spare parts, and other components	
Accessories	USB-C cable 0,5 m
Sterilization / cleaning of accessories	List of recommended disinfectants for transducer soaking or wiping
Consumables / reagents	N/A
Spare parts	Spare parts to be replaced on a regular basis
Other components	Medical-grade power supply ACM18US05
Maintenance	
Maintenance tasks	<p>The measurement system must always be kept in a safe and reliable working order and should be checked regularly, at least once a year, by the manufacturer or authorized persons. The check covers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Inspection for potential mechanical and functional damage. – Readability and integrity of safety labels. – Function test of the device.

Table 9. Specifications of the Linear Array ultrasound transducer by VERMON.

General information	
Generic name	Linear array transducer
Type	Hardware
Version	<i>Latest released version</i>
Author	VERMON
Mechanical structure	
Technology	Piezocomposite, PZT ceramic
Transducer Type:	Linear Array - LA 6.0/128-2886
Number of elements	128
Element pitch	0.3 mm
Elevation aperture	6 mm
Curvature radius (convex, mm)	N/A
Acoustic lens radius (mm)	N/A
Angle element pitch (convex, deg)	N/A

Elevation focus	30 mm	
Housing shape	rectangular parallelepiped (see D 3.1)	
External dimensions of housing (LxWxH)	90x25x20 mm	
Handling by-hand	Detachable ergonomic handle.	
Electrical specifications		
Central Frequency at -6dB	5.4 – 6.6 MHz	
Fractional Bandwidth at -6dB	≥60 min	
Pulse Width at -20dB (us MAX):	≤900 ns	
Cable specifications		
Cable Type:	AWG size 44	
Outer Diameter	6.2±0.3 mm	
Number of coax wires:	135	
Length	2 m	
Capacitance	60±7(pF/m)	
Connector specifications		
Connector Type	ArtUs-Compact (Telemed specific)	
Connector Pinout	ArtUs-Compact (Telemed specific)	
Operating environment		
Operating temperature range	+10 to +40 °C	
Operating relative humidity range	10 % to 80 %	
Operating atmospheric pressure range	700 hPa to 1060 hPa	
Storage Temperature Range	-20 to +55 °C	
Storage relative Humidity Range	10% to 85 % RH	
Storage Atmospheric Pressure Range	500 hPa to 1060 hPa	
Safety and reliability tests		
Salt Immersion Test	Salt solution (saline) immersion	
Dielectric Strength (HIPOT) Test	HIPOT soaking limit (HIPOT specification: 1500 V AC)	
Leakage Current Test*	≤ 50 µA at 264 V AC	
Disinfection and sterilization		
Commercially available compatible disinfectants	Provided in the following list	
Compatible product	Alkazyme	Korsolex Basic
	Bodedex Forte	Korsolex Extra
	Bomix Plus	Mikrozid

	Cavi Wipes XL	Mikrozid AF
	Cidex 2%	Prolystica 2X
	Cidex OPA	Protex Wipes
	Cidex Plus	Metrizyme
	Cidezime	Salvanios PH10
	Gigasept AF	Steranios
	Gigasept FF	Klenzyme
	Incidin Foam S	
Biocompatibility test reports		
Patient contact material	Reports provided, tests passed	
Acoustic lens	Silicone	
Seam line acoustic lens housing	Silicone	
Housing	Plastic	
Seam line housing (2 halves)	Glue	

Table 10. Specifications of the Row-Column Array ultrasound transducer by VERMON.

General information	
Generic name	Row-Column array transducer
Type	Hardware
Author	VERMON
Mechanical structure	
Technology	Piezocomposite, PZT ceramic
Transducer Type	Row-Column Array - RCA 6.0/96+32-2887
Number of Elements	128 (Azimuth: 96/ Elevation: 32)
Element Pitch (mm)	Azimuth: 0.3 / Elevation:0.2
Elevation Aperture (mm)	Azimuth: 6.4 / Elevation: 28.8
Electrical specifications	
Central Frequency at -6dB	5.4 – 6.6 MHz
Fractional Bandwidth at -6dB	≥ 60 min
Cable specifications	
Cable Type	AWG size 44
Outer Diameter	6.2±0.3(mm)
Number of coaxial wires	135
Length	2 m
Capacitance	60±7 pF/m
Connector specifications	
Connector Type	ArtUs-Compact (Telemed specific)

Connector Pinout	ArtUs-Compact (Telemed specific)	
Operating environment		
Operating Temperature Range	+10 to +40 °C	
Operating Relative Humidity Range	10 % to 80 %	
Operating Atmospheric Pressure Range	700 hPa to 1060 hPa	
Storage Temperature Range	-20 to +55 °C	
Storage relative Humidity Range	10% to 85 % RH	
Storage Atmospheric Pressure Range	500 hPa to 1060 hPa	
Safety and reliability tests available		
Tests description	Salt solution (saline) immersion	
Dielectric Strength (Hipot) Test	HIPOT soaking limit (HIPOT specification : 1500 V AC)	
Leakage Current Test*	≤ 50 μA at 264 V AC	
Disinfection and sterilization		
Commercially available compatible disinfectants	Provided in following list	
Compatible product	Alkazyme	Korsolex Basic
	Bodedex Forte	Korsolex Extra
	Bomix Plus	Mikrozid
	Cavi Wipes XL	Mikrozid AF
	Cidex 2%	Prolystica 2X
	Cidex OPA;	Protex Wipes
	Cidex Plus	Metrizyme
	Cidezyme	Salvanios PH10
	Gigasept AF	Steranios
	Gigasept FF	Klenzyme
	Incidin Foam S	
Biocompatibility test reports		
Patient contact material	Reports provided, tests passed	
Acoustic lens	Silicone	
Seam line acoustic lens-housing	Silicone	
Housing	Plastic	
Seam line Housing (2 halves)	Glue	

Table 11. Specifications of the Linear MEMS-based ultrasound transducer by FRAUNHOFER.

General information	
Generic name	Linear array transducer
Type	Hardware
Author	Fraunhofer IPMS
Mechanical structure	
Technology	MEMS
Transducer Type	Real 96 Channel Linear Array with Preamplifiers and Multiplexer
Number of Elements	96 (multiplexed to 8 amplifier channels)
Element Pitch	0.2 mm
Elevation Aperture	5 mm
Curvature Radius	∞ (convex, mm)
Acoustic Lens Radius	∞ (mm)
Angle Element Pitch	0° (convex, deg°)
Elevation Focus	18 mm (4.4 MHz) mm
Probe housing HxWxD	16x94x27 mm
Coating material	Silicone
Coating impedance	$1.6 \cdot 10^6 \text{ kg} \cdot \text{m}^2 \cdot \text{s}$
Handling by hand	Ergonomic handle
Electrical specifications	
Central Frequency at -6dB	4.4(MHz)
Fractional Bandwidth at -6dB	70% (min)
Max Allowed AC Voltage (TX)	0 to -100 V
Max Allowed DC Voltage (Vbias)	0 to +120 V
Average Capacitance	12pF per channel without cables
Electronics for multiplexing of 8 amplifier channels	Included in transducer housing with additional power cables
Ultrasonic RF signals output to beamformer	$\pm 1 \text{ V}$ output level @ 50 Ω
Multiplexer and amplifier electronics powering supply	+5 @ 300 (not included from FIPMS), V @ mA
MEMS array transducer bias voltage HV DC Power supply	0 to +120 (included from FIPMS), Vdc
High-voltage power supply separate module	Included from FIPMS
Cable specifications	
Cable Type	24x AWG32 coax
Outer Diameter	7 mm

Number of coax wires	24
Length	2 m
Capacitance	100 pF/m
High-voltage cable	Included
Supply power separate module	+5 @ 65 Vdc @ mAdc, included
Connector specifications	
Connector Type	ArtUs-Compact (Telemed specific)
Connector Pinout	ArtUs-Compact (Telemed specific)
Strain Relief Type	DBM-4
IP Code	DCP-0
Operating environment	
Operating Temperature Range	+15 to +40 °C
Operating Relative Humidity Range	20% to 55% non condensing
Operating Atmospheric Pressure Range	850 to 1050 kPa
Storage Temperature Range	10 to +50 °C
Storage relative Humidity Range	10% to 90 % non-condensing
Storage Atmospheric Pressure Range	650 hPa to 1150 kPa
Safety and reliability tests	
Tests description	Not characterized
Dielectric Strength (Hipot) Test	Not characterized
Leak Test*	Smaller than $\sim < \mu\text{A}$
Drop Test	Drops need to be avoided
Water-proof IP Code (excluding connector)	IPX7
Disinfection and sterilization	
Commercially available compatible disinfectants	Provided in the following list
Compatible product	Cavi Wipes XL
	Cleansept Wipes
	Protex Wipes
Biocompatibility test reports	
Patient contact material	For demonstrator reason no biocompatibility tests are done with the probe at Fraunhofer IPMS
Human skin touchable materials	Coating (sealing) layer
	Applicator surface
	Housing

Applicator surface	FR4 - glass-reinforced epoxy
Protecting (sealing) layer	Sylgard 160 (silicone)
Housing	Stainless steel 1.4301 also X5CrNi18-10
High-voltage power supply	
Output voltage	+100 to +150 Vdc
Ripple	< 100 mVpp
Noise	< 50 mVrms
DC- HV DC converter (the safer version in medical environment) input to output voltage	12 to 500 Vdc
DC- HV DC converter to output current	3 mAdc
DC- HV DC converter output ripple	< 0.1 %
Power network	230 V 50 Hz, ±10%
Housing	Compact PCB mount package with low ripple and low EMI/RFI

3.2.2. Software

TELEMED designs beamformers that transfer raw ultrasound RF data and stream B-mode images to a PC via a USB3 interface. Optionally, researchers are provided with a MATLAB graphical user interface (GUI) for imaging and data recording, which can be used with either the ArtUs beamformer or the Thrombus+ dedicated beamformer. This GUI serves as a software prototyping environment, where dedicated functionalities are implemented and modified for project-specific purposes. Some functionalities for the real-time assessment of ultrasonic RF data can be adapted from the clinical software Echo Wave II (Figure 4). Newly developed functionalities in MATLAB will be integrated into the Thrombus+ controlling software using new DLL libraries. Integration of new functionalities are developed by ATHENA. Table 12 presents the software related to the Ultrasound Monitoring Module, for controlling the beamformer and acquiring ultrasound data. Figure 4 presents a block diagram of the USGFW2 SDK.

Table 12. Specifications of the USM related software.

General information	
Generic name	Ultrasonography for Windows Software Development Kit (USGFW2 SDK) and TELEMED drivers' package (TDP)
Type	Software
Operating System	Windows 11 or higher (64-bit)
Programming Languages	Native C++
Version	<i>Latest released version</i>
Author	TELEMED
Dependencies	
Runtime	The latest .NET runtime

Other SDK	Microsoft DirectX SDK
Drivers	Standard USB hardware drivers
Redistributable	Visual C++
Interface technology	Microsoft COM (Component Object Model)
Possible programming languages	Native C++, managed C++, C#, VB
SDK functional scope	
Supported modes 8	B-mode
	M-mode
	Doppler
Device enumeration	Beamformer, Transducer
Focusing	Static
	Changeable
	Multi-focus
	Dynamic
Scan-conversion	B-mode scan-converter
	M-mode scan-converter
Filters	Frame averaging,
	Ultrasonic signal rejection
	2D-convolution (Region of Interest-based)
Time-depended processing	Time gain control (TGC)
	Automatic gain control (AGC)
	Time frequency control (TFC)
Controls and settings	Gain
	Power
	Dynamic range
	Frequency presets
Configuration	
Predefined settings	B-mode images of size 512 x 512 pixels - 8bits
Adjustable settings	Frequency presets: 4-5-6 MHz
	Depth: 20 to 120 cm
	Gain: 10 to 90 %,
	Power: -20 to 0 dB
	Dynamic range: 36 to 102 dB
	TGC: 0 to 100% in five depth zones
Adjustable settings	
Adjustable parameters	Imaging mode

	Depth of imaging
	Width of imaging
	Receiver gain range
	Emission power range
	Dynamic range
	Frequency range
	Focal depth
	Time - gain control
Advanced gamma control	8 fixed curves of image intensity compression
Caliper measurement	Distance (mm)
	Area (mm ²)
	Angle (degrees)
	Blood-flow speed (cm/s)
Compatibility & Integration	
Data types	char
	int16
	int32
	uint32
SDK integration	USGFW2 SDK will be integrated in USM app run by the CHI
Security Requirements	
Authentication	Windows Power User
Data Privacy	Controlled USM app run CHI
Audit logging	Log file
Maintenance	
Update mechanism	Manual installation of updated drivers
Error handling	Auto-recorded into log file
Communication & Connectivity	
Data Transmission	USB
Data Formats	Binary sequences of array data
Data Storage	Binary files of RF data (.bin) and image data (.bin)

Figure 4. Block diagram of the USGFW2 SDK. Only the blocks in gray are developed by TELEMED.

3.3. Wearable Actuator Module (WAM)

Wearable Actuator Module (WAM) is developed for two DVT monitoring methods (CDUS and VOP) and thus in two form factors. The first form factor is dedicated to the implementation of Compression Duplex Ultrasound (CDUS) method and consists of two semi-rigid C-type shells with wearable textiles and integrates a detachable US transducer into one of the frames. The other frame contains two air bladders. The inflation and deflation patterns of both bladders are controlled by signals from the central hub & intelligence (CHI) module via USB connected electronic actuator controller (EAC). The ability to regulate air pressure in each bladder ensures the continuous presence of veins within the scanning plane of the transducer, enabling the steering of the ultrasound transducer relative to the vein. The measurement of pressure in both bladders using pressure sensors provides local feedback and ensures safety against overpressure. The second form factor of the WAM utilizes the same EAC but features a different wearable structure (see Deliverable D2.4, Ch. 2.2) suitable for implementing the venous occlusion plethysmography (VOP) method. Input data for controlling bladder pressure, output data on the module's status, and data from pressure sensors are transmitted via a USB-C cable connected to the CHI module.

3.3.1. Hardware

Table 13 presents the Wearable Actuator Module (WAM) specifications.

Table 13. Wearable actuator module (WAM) specifications.

General information	
Generic name	Wearable Actuator Module
Type	Hardware and firmware
Version	<i>Latest released version</i>
Author	KTU
Technical characteristics	
Inflation patterns	Fully controllable from CHI
Communication (input)	Via USB-C from CHI
Pump technology	Pneumatic piezoelectric (ultrasonic) micropump
Exhaust valves	Normally open quick exhaust valves for safety for each bladder
Number of bladders	2
Number of pressure sensors	2 (monitoring each bladder separately)
Number of pumps	2
Input (air) filtration	< 3µm membrane filter (for each pump)
Operational noise	< 40 dB (20 Hz – 20kHz)
Power supply	Via a USB-C from the CHI device
Response time	Ultrafast, millisecond response time
Pressure range	0 – 150 mmHg
Free flow rate	2.2 L/min (continuous) and 2.7 L/min (intermittent) (combined)
Maximum pressure	150 mmHg (continuous) and 188 mmHg (intermittent)
Displayed parameters	Returns pressure readings, time stamps, and data on WAM module status
User adjustable	The Velcro straps and tension-mounting system, wearable on the thigh, are adjustable for the patient
Mechanical characteristics of WAM for CDUS (C-shell type Semirigid Wearable (CSW) option)	
The inner circumference of the adjustable WAM frames	Approximately 38-63 cm
The total quantity of C-shaped frames per WAM	2
Size of the insert for the US transducer in one of the WAM frames	Rectangular slot, with internal dimensions of 90x25x15 mm
Envelope of the frame	Fabric: textile combination of rigid Polyamide and soft fabric composed of Polyamide and Elastane
Inflatable bladder size	Approximately: 110 x 60 mm (2 units) or 220 x 100 mm (1 unit).
Electronic Actuator Controller (EAC) dimensions.	Approximately 90 x 90 x 40 mm
Mechanical characteristics of WAM for VOP (Wearable Thigh Cuff (WTC) option)	

Number of bladders	1
Inflatable bladder size	Approximately 280 x 110 mm
Circumference of the envelope for mounting on the thigh	Regulated by Velcro straps (≤ 50 cm)
Envelope material	Fabric: textile combination of rigid Polyamide and soft fabric composed of Polyamide and Elastane
Physical and chemical characteristics	
Components	Two bladders with two rigid C-shaped frames and associated textiles, wearable actuator electronics module, and USB type-C cable.
Raw materials	Enclosure – PLA (biocompatible), C-shaped frames – PLA (biocompatible). Textile materials in contact with the skin are biocompatible and provide reliable skin contact with comfort
Utility and environmental requirements	
Power	USB-C 5V @ 1.5A max
Context-dependent requirements	Capable of being stored continuously in ambient temperature of 0 to 50 deg C and relative humidity of 15 to 90%
	Capable of operating continuously in the ambient temperature of 10 to 40 deg C and relative humidity of 15 to 90%
Accessories, consumables, spare parts, and other components	
Accessories	USB-C cable 1,5 m
Sterilization / cleaning of accessories	The textiles of the actuator can be washed
Consumables / reagents	-
Spare parts	Spare parts are to be replaced regularly
Other components	-
Maintenance	
Maintenance tasks	Verification of the integrity and connection of air tubes, connectors, and external housing before each use
Upgrade tasks	Firmware upgrade through a dedicated GUI application

3.3.2. Software

Table 14 presents the specification the WAM related software.

Table 14. Specifications of the WAM related software.

General information	
Generic name	WAM_SDK
Type	Software and firmware
Operating systems	Windows 11 or higher (64-bit) The latest .NET runtime
Programming languages	C and C++ (for ESP32 microcontroller)

Firmware	EAC
Version	<i>Latest released version</i>
Author	KTU
Software requirements	
Programming language	C
Communication protocol	Communication with the WAM module is achieved via USB-C type cable and USB communications device class (CDC). Serial communication is 115200 8-N-1.
Functional scope	
Data streaming	Status and Pressure sensor reading responses are constructed on the device, depending on the actual pump module and valve states.
Application programming interface (API)	Text-based commands should be sent to the WAM module. All commands are terminated by carriage return symbol '\r' (ASCII CR). Every command received is responded to by echoing the command back or "ERR\r" if the wrong command is received. The full list of the commands is presented in the deliverable D3.3.
GUI application	A dedicated GUI application for the testing and maintenance of the WAM component.
Technical characteristics	
Supported algorithms	Closed loop pressure control by pressure sensor readings for each pump
Core functionalities	Collect and transmit device Status and pressure sensor readings Receive control commands for pump and valve control
Configuration	
Predefined settings	Approximately 62Hz sampling rate for pressure sensors Pump power 1000mW Slow-release valves open Exhaust valves open
Adjustable settings	1-62Hz sampling rate Enable/Disable pumps Set desired inflation pressure Close/Open slow-release valves Close/Open exhaust valves
Compatibility & Integration	
APIs	WAM_SDK.dll
Protocols	Virtual Com Port over USB connection
Baudrate	115200 bps
Data mode	8-N-1
Command termination	Carriage return symbol ('\r')
Maintenance	
Update mechanism	Via dedicated GUI
Error handling	Error codes in Status Report
Communication & Connectivity	

Data transmission	Wired, by USB cable
Data formats	Text-based (ASCII) input for commands and readings as output
Data storage	No internal storage present

3.4. Electrical Impedance Module (EIM)

3.4.1. Hardware

Table 15 presents the electrical impedance module (EIM) specifications.

Table 15. Electrical impedance module (EIM) specifications.

General information	
Generic name	Electrical Impedance Module
Type	Hardware and firmware
Version	<i>Latest released version</i>
Author	TAU
Technical characteristics	
Measuring principle	Single- and multifrequency impedance plethysmography
Electrode configuration	Bipolar, tetrapolar
Excitation frequency	Up to 20 adjustable frequencies in the range of 10-500 kHz
Excitation current	Adjustable: up to 2.9 mA
Impedance measurement range	0.1-400 Ω
Sampling rate	Adjustable: 25, 50, 100 or 200 Hz
Communication	Wi-Fi
Power	Rechargeable lithium polymer battery
Battery voltage	3.7 V
Battery capacity	4500 mAh
Battery charging	Via a USB Type-C connector during non-use periods
Displayed parameters	Impedance plethysmography signal in the time domain, time stamps, EIP-extracted parameters (at least venous capacity and outflow values), data on EIM status (charge level, measurement status, data recording status)
User adjustable settings	Selection between single-frequency and multi-frequency measurements, the number of excitation frequencies measured simultaneously, Excitation frequency, selection between bipolar and tetrapolar configurations, excitation current, sampling rate, electrode tension
Physical and chemical characteristics	
Components	EIM controller: Two controllers for bilateral measurement.
	EIM controller dimensions: 157 x 89 x 26 mm
	EIM controller weight: 257 g

	Textile electrodes for both legs: Four electrodes for both legs: two outer electrodes for current injection and two inner for voltage measurement. Electrodes are adjustable and washable and integrated into a wearable system.
Sterilization / cleaning of components	Textile electrodes can be washed with mild detergent in common washing machines at 30°C.
Raw materials	For EIM controller: ABS plastic housing, lithium polymer battery (LP123497), PVC insulated electrode wires
	For the textile electrodes: Silver-plated fabric OEKO-TEX® STANDARD 100 certified
Environmental conditions	
Transport and storage conditions	Temperature: 0 to 50 °C
	Humidity: 15 to 95 % (non-condensing)
	Altitude: 0 to 3000 m
	Atmospheric pressure: 400 hPa to 1100 hPa
Operating conditions	Temperature: 10 to 30 °C
	Humidity: 30 to 75 % (non-condensing)
	Atmospheric pressure: 700 hPa to 1050 hPa
	Altitude: 0 to 3000 m
Accessories, consumables, spare parts, and other components	
Accessories	USB-C cable 1.5 m
	Electrode connection wires with safety connector and snap: Four wires for both legs
Consumables / reagents	-
Spare parts	Spare parts are to be replaced regularly
	Electroconductive textile-based electrodes keep their functions after several washing cycles if washing instructions are followed
Other components	-
Maintenance	
Maintenance tasks	Checking the integrity of wires, connectors, and external housing before each use. Washing textile electrodes regularly and between patients

3.4.2. Software

Table 16 presents the EIM-related software specifications.

Table 16. Electrical Impedance Module-related software specifications.

General information	
Generic name	EIM Software
Type	Software and firmware
SDK and related firmware	EIM
Version	<i>Latest released version</i>

Author	TAU
Dependencies	
Operating System	Windows 11 or higher (64-bit)
Runtime	The latest .NET runtime
Physical communication medium	Wi-Fi, 802.11b/g/n
Firmware programming language	C (for ATSAM4S8B microcontroller)
Software programming language	C# (for PC)
SDK functional scope	
Discovery mode	mDNS (automatic IP address configuration)
Device status	IP, connected state
Device configuration	Selection between single-frequency and multi-frequency measurements
	The number of excitation frequencies measured simultaneously
	Excitation frequency
	Selection between bipolar and tetrapolar configurations
	Excitation current
	Sampling rate
Real-time data streaming	TCP protocol using a fixed binary structure that includes data from EIM sensor
Heartbeat mechanism	Maintains and detects connectivity, otherwise reverts to discovery mode
Specialised algorithms	Self-calibration
	Excitation waveform calculation
	Presentation of the measurement data as impedances
	Feature extraction
	Diagnostic classifiers
GUI application	A dedicated GUI application for the testing and maintenance of the EIM component
Technical characteristics	
Functionalities	Start measurement
	Stop measurement
	Record data
	Adjust measurement settings
Non-Functionalities	N/A
User Interface (UI)	
UI Components	Start button
	Stop button
	Device setting section

	Results section
Data Display Formats	Real-time impedance signal
	EIP-extracted parameters
Accessibility	According to the medical device requirements
Configuration	
Predefined Settings	N/A
Adjustable Settings	Selection between single-frequency and multi-frequency measurements
	The number of excitation frequencies measured simultaneously: Up to 20
	Excitation frequencies: 10-500 kHz
	Selection between bipolar and tetrapolar configurations
	Excitation current: Maximum peak amplitude 2.9 mA
	Sampling rate: 25, 50, 100 or 200 Hz
Compatibility & Integration	
APIs	EIM_SDK.dll
Protocols	Communication protocol: TCP
Third-Party Integrations	N/A
Security Requirements	
Authentication	N/A
Data Privacy	N/A (Data anonymity)
Audit Logging	Logging for user actions, system errors, and security events
Maintenance	
Update Mechanism	Manual installations for EIM device
Error handling	Exporting error stack trace and related metrics
Communication & Connectivity	
Data Transmission	TCP for communication
Data Formats	Sequences of vector data
Data Storage	Binary file, MATLAB (.mat file)

3.5. Light Rheography Module (LRM)

3.5.1. Hardware

Table 17 presents the main hardware specifications of the light reflection module (LRM).

Table 17. Light rheography module (LRM) specifications.

General information	
Generic name	Light rheography module
Type	Hardware and firmware

Version	<i>Latest released version</i>
Author	medis
Technical characteristics	
Main characteristics	An optical rheography measuring channel is implemented in the device. The technical parameters can be found in detail in the table below.
Displayed parameters	Venous blood displacement volume, refilling time.
User adjustable settings	None
Electrical and mechanical specification	
Power	Rechargeable battery
Charging method	Wired charging using a magnetic force connector
Charging power	Max. 0,5 W (100 mA @ 5 V using an USB-A connector)
Wavelength	950 nm
Light source	Infrared light, pulsed light source
Frequency range	0 to 3 Hz
Status display	RGB LED
Dimensions	Almost round case, diameter: 45 mm; height: 15 mm
Weight	Approx. 20 g
Length of the charging cable	Approx. 50 cm
Environmental Conditions	
Transport and storage conditions	Temperature: 0 to 50 °C
	Humidity: 15 to 95 % (non-condensing)
	Altitude: 0 to 3000 m
	Atmospheric pressure: 400 hPa to 1100 hPa
Operating conditions	Temperature: 10 to 30 °C
	Humidity: 30 to 75 % (non-condensing)
	Atmospheric pressure: 650 hPa to 1050 hPa
	Altitude: 0 to 3000 m
Safety tests	
IEC 60601-1	Not yet carried out
IEC 60601-1-2	Not yet carried out
IP Protection	Not yet carried out
Disinfection and sterilization	
Cleaning and Disinfection:	The sensors must be carefully cleaned and disinfected after each skin contact
	Clean and disinfect the sensors by wiping all contact surfaces
	Follow the hygienic procedures of the users hospital/facility
Compatible product:	Cloth damped with a 70% isopropyl alcohol solution, e.g., Prolystica® / STERIS plc., terralin® protect / Schülke & Mayr GmbH

Biocompatibility test report	
Part of contact:	Housing LRR Sensor (Not intended, but possible)
	Material identification and evaluation available
User contact material:	Thermoplastic polymer; Polypropylene copolymer; biocompatible
Contact duration and classification acc. to EN ISO 10993-1	< 30 min / A - short time (<= 24 h)
Accessories, consumables, spare parts, and other components	
Accessories	Associated textile wearable
Sterilization / cleaning of accessories	Associated textile wearable can be washed in a common washing machine at 30°C, with all electronics removed.
Consumables / reagents	Associated textile wearable
Spare parts	None
Maintenance	
Maintenance tasks	<p>The measurement system must always be kept in safe and reliable working order and should be checked regularly, at least once a year, by the manufacturer or authorized persons. The check covers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Inspection for potential mechanical and functional damage – Readability and integrity of safety labels – Function test of the device.

3.5.2. Software

Table 18 presents the LRM-related software specifications:

Table 18. Light reflection module-related software specifications.

General information	
Generic name	LRM Software
Type	Software and firmware
SDK and related firmware	LRM
Version	Latest released version
Author	medis
Dependencies	
Operating system	Windows 11 or higher (64-bit)
Runtime	The latest .NET runtime
Physical communication medium	Wi-Fi, 802.11ac
Firmware programming language	C (for ESP32 microcontroller)
Software programming language	C# (for PC)
SDK functional scope	

Discovery mode	mDNS (automatic IP address configuration)
Device status and configuration	IP, connected state, set appropriate LED current
Real-time data streaming	UDP protocol using a fixed binary structure that includes data from LRM sensor.
Heartbeat mechanism	Maintains and detects connectivity, otherwise reverts to discovery mode
Specialised algorithms	Calculation of venous blood displacement volume and refilling time
GUI application	A dedicated GUI application for the testing and maintenance of the LRM component.
Technical characteristics	
Functional requirements	Start measurement, stop measurement, record data, calculate parameters
Non-functional requirements	N/A
Dependencies	N/A
User Interface (UI)	
UI components	Start button, stop button, guidance pictures show feet positions, metronome sound
Data display formats	Real time curve of venous emptying and refilling phase, calculated parameters
Accessibility	According to the medical device requirements
Configuration	
Predefined settings	N/A
Adjustable settings	N/A
Compatibility & Integration	
APIs	LRM_SDK.dll
Protocols	Communication protocol: TCP
Third-Party Integrations	N/A
Security Requirements	
Authentication	N/A
Data privacy	N/A
Audit logging	Logging for user actions, system errors
Maintenance	
Update mechanism	Manual updates
Error handling	Export of system errors
Communication & Connectivity	
Data transmission	TCP for communication
Data formats	ASCII data
Data storage	Text file

3.6. Limb Activity Module (LAM)

3.6.1. Hardware

Table 19 presents the main hardware specifications of the limb activity module (LAM).

Table 19. Limb activity module specifications.

General information	
Generic name	Limb Activity Module
Type	Hardware, firmware and software
Version	<i>Latest released version</i>
Author	KTU
Technical characteristics	
Activity and orientation sensor	ICM20948 inertial measurement unit MEMS sensor
Accelerometer range	± 8 g
Gyroscope range	± 2000 deg/s
Magnetometer range	± 4900 μ T
Orientation estimation accuracy	RMSE = ± 5 degs
Temperature sensor	MAX90632 non-contact temperature sensor.
Temperature resolution	0.01 °C
Temperature accuracy	± 0.2 °C
Sensor node controller device	STM32 microcontroller
Auxiliary PPG sensor	MAX86916 integrated optical sensor platform
Sensor nodes connection to LAM controller	USART to full duplex M-LVDS, Single 1.27 mm pitch ribbon cable
LAM controller device	ESP32 S3 microcontroller
LAM connection to CHI	Wi-Fi, UDP protocol
SD Card	Micro-SD, 32 Gb
Datal collection rate	Up to 50 Hz
Battery	18650 type Li-ion battery, removable
Battery voltage	3.6 V
Battery capacity	12.6 Wh
Battery charging	USB-C connector. Device not operational while charging
Displayed parameters on the LAM controller screen	State: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Ready 2) Measuring 3) Error 4) Error number Battery status:

	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Charge level (%) 1) 2) Charging
Returned parameters	To CHI via Wi-Fi: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Sensor readings 2) Time stamps 2) 3) LAM module status data
User adjustable settings (by CHI)	Data collection frequency can be changed from 1 to 50 Hz
	PPG measurement can be enabled or disabled
Physical and chemical characteristics	
Sensors	Cases made from bio-compatible PLA, glass, or bio-compatible epoxy in areas of skin contact. Printed circuit board with RoHS-compliant components; no direct patient contact.
Sensors dimensions	Cylindrical, d = 20 mm, h = 10 mm
Ribbon cable	Poly-Vinyl Chloride insulation, 1.27 mm pitch, 28 AWG
LAM controller	Casing from bio-compatible PLA
LAM controller dimensions	Rectangular, measuring 97 × 58 × 22 mm, with a 29 mm connector extending from its length, and weighing no more than 300 g
Utility and environmental requirements	
Charging source	USB-C 5V @ 1.5A max
Transport and storage conditions	Temperature: 0 to 50 °C
	Humidity: 15 to 95 % (non-condensing)
	Altitude: 0 to 3000 m
	Atmospheric pressure: 400 hPa to 1100 hPa
Operating conditions	Temperature: 10 to 30 °C
	Humidity: 30 to 75 % (non-condensing)
	Atmospheric pressure: 650 hPa to 1050 hPa
	Altitude: 0 to 3000 m
Accessories, consumables, spare parts, and other components	
Accessories	Associated textile wearable
	USB-C cable 1.5 m
Sterilization / cleaning of accessories	Associated textile wearable can be washed in a common washing machine at 30°C, with all electronics removed
	Skin-contact area of the sensors can be disinfected using standard medical disinfectants
Spare parts	Ribbon cable for LAM controller and sensors connection
Maintenance	
Maintenance tasks	The measurement system must always be kept in safe and reliable working order, by checking the integrity of wires, connectors, body and casings before each use.
	The measurement system must be checked at least once a year by the manufacturer or authorized persons. The check covers:

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Inspection for potential mechanical and functional damage – Verification of readability and integrity of safety labels – Functional testing of the device
Safety tests	
IEC 60601-1	Not yet carried out
IEC 60601-1-2	Not yet carried out
IP Protection	Not yet carried out

3.6.2. Software

Table 20 presents the Limb Activity Module-related software specifications.

Table 20. Limb activity module-related software specifications.

General information	
Generic name	LAM_SDK
Type	Software and firmware
Version	<i>Latest released version</i>
Author	KTU
Dependencies	
Operating System	Windows 11 or higher (64-bit)
Runtime	The latest .NET runtime
Physical communication medium	Wi-Fi, 802.11ac
Firmware programming language	C and C++ (for STM32 and ESP32 microcontrollers)
Software programming language	C# (for PC)
SDK functional scope	
Discovery mode	mDNS (automatic IP address configuration)
Device status and configuration	IP, connected state, streaming state sampling rate
Real-time data streaming	UDP protocol using a fixed binary structure that includes data from IMU, PPG, and temperature sensors.
Heartbeat mechanism	Maintains and detects connectivity, otherwise reverts to discovery mode
GUI application	A dedicated GUI application for the testing and maintenance of the LAM component.
Technical characteristics	
Supported algorithms	Real-time estimation of orientation angles (quaternions)
Core functionalities	Collect and transmit leg segments' orientation data
	Collect and transmit raw activity data
	Collect and transmit temperature data
	Collect and transmit PPG data
Configuration	

Default settings	50Hz sampling rate
	Orientation data enabled
	Raw activity data disabled
	Temperature measurement enabled
	PPG measurement disabled
	SD card recording enabled
Adjustable settings	1-50 Hz Sampling Rate
	Enable/Disable orientation data transmission
	Enable/Disable raw data transmission
	Enable/Disable temperature
	Enable/Disable PPG measurement
	Enable/Disable SD card recording
Compatibility & Integration	
APIs	LAM_SDK.dll
External protocols	TCP, UDP
Internal protocols	USART
Security Requirements	
Authentication	Module authenticated by UUID
Data privacy	WiFi WPA3 encoded
Maintenance	
Update mechanism	Via dedicated GUI
Error handling	Error codes in Status Report
Communication & Connectivity	
Data transmission	TCP – for commands UDP – for data
Data formats	Data transmission in TLV (Tag Length Value) Data storage in GDF (General Biomedical Data Format)
Data storage	SD card

Figure 5 presents a block diagram of the LAM module firmware and associated software (SDK) architecture.

Figure 5. Block diagram of the software architecture of the limb activity module (LAM).

3.7. Extended Reality & Serious Gaming Module (XGM)

3.7.1. Software

Table 21 presents the specification for the extended reality & serious gaming module (XGM).

Table 21. Extended reality & serious gaming module (XGM) specifications.

General information	
Generic name	Extended reality & serious gaming module
Type	Software.
Operating Systems	Windows 11 or higher (64-bit)
Programming Languages	C# (for PC)
Version	<i>Latest released version</i>
Author	ATHENA
Technical characteristics	

Detailed requirements	Extended reality (XR) technology integrates advanced inertial measurement unit (IMU) sensors to capture and process real-time movement data with high precision. This project utilizes the Unity game engine to create an immersive 3D simulation environment, where IMU sensors provide real-time orientation, rotation, and acceleration data. The collected data is structured and mapped onto a 3D model in .fbx format, incorporating skeletal and skin details for accurate motion representation.
	The XR and serious gaming module runs on a PC equivalent to a computing system with a dedicated graphics card, not an integrated one, and at least 8GB of RAM, ensuring smooth visualization and interaction. This system is designed for healthcare applications, enabling precise motion tracking and rehabilitation support
Displayed parameters	A dedicated interface allows physiotherapists to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – prescribe and manage rehabilitation programs, – browse, search, preview, and select exercises, – define exercise sequences and set parameters such as the number of repetitions and sets
User adjustable settings	The XR module operates using a predefined set of rehabilitation exercises, which physiotherapists can customize based on individual patient needs.
Dependencies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Unity game engine (Unity 3D) for the XR simulation. – C# (.NET environment on Windows 11 or higher). – IMU sensor hardware along with necessary drivers. – CHI (WinForm C# application) for integration via process embedding. – Websocket and REST API (over TCP).
Maintenance	
Maintenance tasks	-
Upgrade tasks	Manual installation of updates
Error handling	Auto-recorded into log file
Technical characteristics	
Dependencies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Unity game engine (Unity 3D) for the XR simulation. – C# (.NET environment on Windows 11 or higher). – IMU sensor hardware along with necessary drivers. – CHI (WinForm C# application) for integration via process embedding. – Communication libraries for WebSocket and REST API (over TCP).
User Interface (UI)	
UI Components	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – 3D simulation viewport for immersive XR visualization. – Dashboard dedicated to physiotherapists. – Control panels for managing rehabilitation programs (prescription, exercise selection, sequence definition).
Data Display Formats	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – 3D model display using .fbx files with detailed skeletal and skin mapping. – Real-time graphs or indicators for visualizing IMU sensor data (binary or text). – Tabular or list views for exercise parameters and program details.
Accessibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Clear, intuitive layout optimized for healthcare professionals.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Scalable UI elements to accommodate various screen resolutions and high-contrast design for visibility. – Consideration for assistive technologies (e.g., screen readers) to enhance usability.
Configuration	
Predefined Settings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – WebSocket Port – IMU data header and format
Adjustable Settings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Customizable exercise parameters (number of repetitions, sets, sequence order) for individual patient needs. – Options to adjust UI preferences and sensor data visualization settings (e.g., refresh rate, precision).
Compatibility & Integration	
APIs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – REST API endpoints for external control commands and status queries. – WebSocket API for real-time streaming of IMU sensor data. – Unity API for embedding the XR module within the CHI application.
Protocols	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – TCP for REST API communications. – WebSocket protocol for live sensor data transmission.
Third-Party Integrations	Integration with the CHI WinForm C# application via process embedding of the Unity runtime.
Security Requirements	
Authentication	Handled by CHI
Data Privacy	Sensor data is handled in-memory
Audit Logging	Handled by CHI
Communication & Connectivity	
Data Transmission	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Real-time streaming via Websockets for IMU sensor data. – REST API communications over TCP for control and status updates.
Data Formats	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – IMU sensor data transmitted as binary or text, depending on implementation requirements. – 3D models provided in .fbx format.
Data Storage	-

4. DVT monitoring methods and working modes

The following chapter describes how the modules described in the previous sections will be used in different configurations to implement DVT monitoring methods.

4.1. Operator-independent Compression Duplex Ultrasonography for DVT monitoring

The Compression Duplex Ultrasonography (CDUS) method is the main method used for DVT detection⁶. It combines B-mode ultrasound imaging with Doppler flow analysis to assess venous compressibility and blood flow. In this method, a transducer is placed over the vein while gentle pressure is applied. A healthy vein compresses completely under pressure, whereas a thrombus prevents full compression, indicating deep vein thrombosis (DVT). Doppler imaging further evaluates blood flow characteristics, detecting abnormalities such as reduced or absent flow, which can suggest the presence of a clot. This technique is widely used due to its high sensitivity and specificity for DVT diagnosis. However, this technique requires highly skilled medical professional or operator.

To implement operator-independent post-surgical monitoring for DVT in a hospital setting, the ThrombUS+ system will combine an ultrasound module (USM) for imaging, a wearable actuator module (WAM) for controlled compression, and a central control and processing unit (CHI) to automate the procedure (see Figure 6).

Figure 6. The ThrombUS+ subsystem for operator-independent Compression Ultrasonography: only the highlighted modules are used in this scenario.

The system will operate in three modes:

⁶ A. W. Lensing et al., “Detection of deep-vein thrombosis by real-time B-mode ultrasonography,” N Engl J Med, vol. 320, no. 6, pp. 342–345, Feb. 1989

Imaging: In this mode, the system is controlled by a **medical specialist, i.e., operator**. Upon activation, the WAM applies controlled, sequential compression to the patient's thigh, mimicking the manual compression performed by a clinician. Simultaneously, the USM captures real-time ultrasound images of the deep veins in the compressed region. Advanced image processing algorithms automatically segment the veins, track their dimensions, and assess their response to compression. The primary objective of this mode is to enable the operator to evaluate the situation, calibrate the system, and personalize the detection thresholds for DVT.

Monitoring: After ThrombUS+ CDUS subsystem is calibrated, it can be switched to autonomous working mode for DVT monitoring. In this mode, CHI will periodically initiate WAM-based compression and USM-based imaging procedure. If a thrombus is present, the system detects abnormal vein behavior, such as incomplete compression or reduced vein collapsibility, which are key indicators of DVT. CHI processes this data in real time and provides an assessment of DVT risk, displaying results for clinical review and initiating a visual and audible alert.

Analysis: When the monitoring stage is finished, the analysis mode can be initiated manually by the operator. During periodic measurements in the monitoring mode, a dataset is generated, consisting of raw ultrasound data and time series of monitored parameters. The analysis mode enables deeper processing, analysis, and visualization of the collected data, identification of trends in extracted features, and potentially machine learning-based anomaly detection.

Any working mode could be initiated and stopped on demand, i.e., at any time by the operator. By enabling operator-independent DVT monitoring, the system reduces reliance on specialized personnel, enhances accessibility to routine screenings, and ensures standardized, objective evaluations of venous thrombosis risk.

4.2. Operator-independent Venous Occlusion Plethysmography for DVT monitoring

Venous Occlusion Plethysmography (VOP) is a non-invasive technique used to assess venous function and detect deep vein thrombosis (DVT) by measuring changes in calf volume during controlled venous occlusion. In this method, a cuff is inflated around the thigh to temporarily obstruct venous outflow while maintaining arterial inflow, leading to a gradual increase in calf volume. The rate of volume change is recorded using plethysmography sensors, such as electrical bioimpedance sensors. In healthy individuals, venous outflow resumes rapidly upon cuff deflation, whereas in DVT, the presence of a thrombus impairs venous drainage, leading to abnormal volume changes. By analyzing these hemodynamic patterns, VOP provides valuable insights into venous obstruction and serves as a diagnostic tool for DVT assessment.

To enable an operator-independent VOP method in a hospital setting, the ThrombUS+ system will integrate an electrical impedance module (EIM) for imaging, a wearable actuator module (WAM) for controlled compression, and a central control and processing unit (CHI) to automate the procedure (see Figure 7). The WAM will repurpose the electronic actuator controller (EAC) from the CDUS subsystem, utilizing a wearable thigh cuff (WTC) instead of the C-shell-type semirigid wearable (CSW) used in CDUS.

The VOP subsystem, similar to the CDUS, will operate in three modes: imaging, monitoring, and analysis. In imaging mode, the system is operated manually. Upon activation, the wearable actuator module (WAM) applies controlled compression to the patient's thigh via the wearable thigh cuff (WTC), just enough to close the veins. As the WTC deflates, the electrical impedance module (EIM) simultaneously registers volume changes. The primary objective of this mode is to allow the operator to evaluate the situation, calibrate the system, and personalize the detection thresholds for deep vein thrombosis (DVT).

Once the ThrombUS+ VOP subsystem is calibrated, it can be switched to **monitoring** mode for autonomous DVT detection. In this mode, the central control and processing unit (CHI) periodically initiates VOP sessions. If a thrombus forms, the system detects an abnormal relationship between venous filling and outflow. The CHI processes this data in real-time, assesses the DVT risk, and triggers an alert if the risk exceeds a predefined threshold. The results are displayed for clinical review, allowing healthcare professionals to take appropriate action.

Figure 7. The ThromBUS+ subsystem for operator-independent Venous Occlusion Plethysmography: only the highlighted modules are used in this scenario.

After the monitoring phase, the **analysis** mode can be manually initiated by the operator. During periodic measurements in monitoring mode, the system generates a dataset consisting of raw bioimpedance data and time-series recordings of monitored parameters. The analysis mode enables in-depth data processing, visualization, and trend identification in extracted features. Additionally, this mode can support machine learning-based anomaly detection, further enhancing the accuracy of DVT assessment.

Any working mode could be initiated and stopped on demand, i.e., at any time by the operator.

4.3. Operator-Independent Light Reflection Rheography-Based Monitoring of DVT

Light Reflection Rheography (LRR) is an optical technique used for monitoring venous function (valve insufficiency) and detecting DVT by assessing changes in blood volume dynamics in the skin microcirculation. It relies on the optical reflectance properties of the skin, which vary based on blood volume fluctuations in the underlying venous network. An infrared light source illuminates the skin, typically over a superficial vein, while a photodiode measures the intensity of the reflected light. When venous occlusion occurs—either through controlled compression (e.g., with a thigh cuff) or natural changes in circulation—variations in blood volume alter the reflectance properties. A healthy venous system exhibits a rapid decrease in reflectance upon venous filling and a quick recovery after occlusion is released. However, in cases of DVT, the presence of a thrombus disrupts normal venous drainage, leading to delayed or reduced reflectance changes.

Foot dorsiflexion or the tiptoe test in a sitting position is a standard procedure used to induce variations in blood volume in the lower limb. During this test, the contraction of calf muscles pushes blood out of the limb. If venous occlusion occurs, potentially due to a thrombus, light reflectance changes will appear, indicating a risk of DVT. However, the standard tiptoe test has an inherent repeatability issue, as it is patient dependent.

The repeatability of the test could be improved through synchronized movement guidance and patient response monitoring (see Figure 8). To achieve this, an optical light reflection module (LRM) will monitor reflectance changes, an extended reality and serious gaming module (XGM) will provide movement guidance, and a limb activity module (LAM) will track the patient's response. Additionally, the central control and processing unit (CHI) will automate the procedure. By integrating these components, LRR method enables not only standardized assessment but also intermittent monitoring of DVT, allowing for early detection of hemodynamic changes and increased DVT risk over time.

Figure 8. The ThrombUS+ subsystem for LRM-based DVT monitoring: only the highlighted modules are used in this scenario.

4.4. Serious Gaming and Extended Reality for DVT prevention and rehabilitation

DVT prevention can be enhanced through the integration of serious gaming and limb activity monitoring, promoting patient engagement and adherence to movement protocols. Serious games, designed with interactive and motivational elements, encourage regular physical activity, reducing the risk of venous stasis—a primary contributor to DVT. When combined with real-time limb activity monitoring, these systems provide objective feedback on movement patterns, also alerting users and healthcare providers to periods of inactivity. This dual approach not only improves patient compliance but also enables personalized interventions, ultimately reducing the incidence of DVT in at-risk populations, such as post-surgical patients or individuals with limited mobility.

Additionally, patients of most of the ThrombUS+ RUCs (i.e. surgery, peripartum, obesity) are normally prescribed physical therapy exercises to promote mobilization, prevent thrombosis, and allow for proper patient physical rehabilitation. In the pilot use case chosen at proposal stage, namely, patients undergoing orthopedic surgery for the lower limb, the physical rehabilitation process includes lower limb exercises prescribed by a physiotherapist. The extended reality environment will provide the platform for these

exercises to be selected by the physiotherapist so that a dynamic physical therapy can be constructed. The extended reality will provide the patient with a virtual physiotherapy coach. The patient will have the opportunity to replay individual exercises and the entire physical therapy prescription and assess their own performance against the model exercises. Real-time visual guides will be provided to help the patient perform the prescribed exercise correctly. A summary of patient activity will be available for the physiotherapist to assess progress and compliance.

Operator-independent serious gaming and the extended reality virtual physical exercise coach for DVT prevention and rehabilitation will be achieved by integrating the XGM module, which provides movement guidance; the LAM module, which tracks the patient’s response to guidance and monitors limb activity over time; and the CHI module, which automates the procedure (Figure 9).

Figure 9. The ThrombUS+ subsystem for DVT prevention: only the highlighted modules are used in this scenario.

In addition, incorporating an LRM could offer the advantage of monitoring the efficiency of prevention exercises by assessing subtle variations in limb movement and muscle engagement. This real-time feedback could further optimize exercise regimens, ensuring their effectiveness in promoting venous circulation and reducing DVT risk.

5. Critical specifications of the ThrombUS+ integrated product

5.1. Core functions

This section outlines the core functional capabilities of the integrated ThrombUS+ system.

5.1.1. Ultrasound imaging for DVT detection in the lower limbs

The novel ultrasound probes, in conjunction with the compact and portable beamformer provide real-time imaging of deep veins in the lower limbs. To achieve operator-independent tissue and therefore, vein

compression, the probe is embedded in a dedicated cuff that also contains two airbladders, connected to the wearable actuator module (WAM). The cuff also provides stability over prolonged use times.

The integrated convolution neural network (CNN) models analyze the ultrasound images in real-time, giving feedback to the beamformer and the electronic actuator controller respectively, via the central hub & intelligence module.

The key functionalities of the ThrombUS+ device, with respect to the ultrasonography are:

1. Real-time image acquisition and processing.
2. Automated image interpretation and DVT detection using AI models.
3. Intermittent or on-demand monitoring modes.

5.1.2. Plethysmography measurements for DVT detection in the lower limbs

The ThrombUS+ device incorporates electrical impedance and light reflection sensors to assess blood flow within the lower limbs. The electrical impedance module in conjugation with the wearable actuator module works synergically to implement the operator independent venous occlusion method, which measures changes in electrical resistance due to blood pooling, indicative of thrombosis presence.

The key functionalities of the ThrombUS+ device, with respect to the plethysmography sensors are:

1. Real-time data acquisition and analysis.
2. Automated data interpretation and DVT detection using AI models.
3. Intermittent or on-demand monitoring modes.

5.1.3. Extended reality environment and serious games for DVT prevention

The ThrombUS+ device also integrates software for patient guidance and motivation on performing prescribed physiotherapy exercises for DVT prevention. The extended reality (XGM) leverages the limb activity module, embedded in the ThrombUS+ wearable, for real-time activity recognition and visualization with the aim of providing a virtual physiotherapy coach. The serious game module leverages the limb activity module as input to drive the game, thus providing an alternative means of engagement with physical activity and, ultimately, supporting DVT prevention.

The key functionalities of the ThrombUS+ device, with respect to DVT prevention are:

1. Real-time visualization of lower limbs and guidance against model physical therapy exercises.
2. Patient motivation via serious gaming.
3. Automated interpretation of patient's progress.

5.1.4. Integrated data processing and visualization

The central hub and intelligence (CHI) module serve as the central node, for synchronizing and controlling the several services required by each measurement mode. In addition, it provides a user friend graphical interface for patients, clinicians and technicians.

The key functionalities of the ThrombUS+ device, with respect to central hub are:

1. Real-time feedback on device's status and sensor reading.
2. Efficient data processing when required.
3. User friendly interface with data visualization capabilities.

5.2. User flow

This section introduces a user flow diagram that maps the entire lifecycle of the ThrombUS+ device. The diagram details how the device transitions from its initial configuration—where the healthcare professional sets up the device and adds a new patient—to a locked state that ensures secure patient usage.

Figure 10 illustrates the user flow of the medical device, detailing the transition between different operational states:

1. Device starts in a configuration state.
2. The clinician (Healthcare Professional - HP) configures the device, such as adding a new patient.
3. After patient selection, the clinician sets up the patient specific device configuration, such as monitoring plan, physiotherapy prescription, and locks the device. If the device is not locked the clinician can have access to manual imaging modes, or to the analysis mode if patient data are available.
4. When the device is locked, patient monitoring mode is activated.
5. After the patient session ends, the device is unlocked by the clinician and data is reviewed.
6. The clinician can either repeat for another patient or conclude the session flow.

Figure 10. ThrombUS+ device user flow diagram.

The process begins in a configuration state, where the Healthcare Professional (HP) sets up the device and prepares it for patient monitoring mode. Once a patient is selected and their profile is configured, the device is locked, ensuring restricted access during the session.

During the session, the patient interacts with the device while it continuously monitors progress and collects sensor data. At the end of the session, the HP unlocks the device, reviews the recorded data, and analyzes patient progress. The HP can then either prepare the device for another patient or conclude the session flow, completing the operational cycle.

This structured flow ensures that the device operates securely, efficiently, and in compliance with medical protocols, facilitating both patient treatment and professional oversight.

5.3. User interfaces

This section outlines the essential interface design for the ThrombUS+ device, highlighting the clear delineation of user roles and access levels within the device’s workflow. Figure 11 presents the workflow of system usage, helping users understand how the device is configured, locked in patient monitoring mode, and reviewed post-session. It ensures that clinicians control device access, manage patient interactions, and oversee data collection, while patients can only access relevant functions in View Mode.

Figure 11. System roles and views.

5.4. System roles and user interface features

This section highlights how the user interface (UI) segregates access by defining distinct roles, ensuring that each user, whether a technician, clinician, or patient, interacts only with the functions pertinent to their responsibilities, thereby enhancing both security and usability.

At the top of Figure 11, the diagram illustrates three primary system roles:

- Clinician (Healthcare Professional - HP): Assist patients on wearing and using the device managing patient data, configuring exercises, and reviewing treatment progress.
- Patient: Interacts with the system in a controlled environment where functionalities are restricted to their prescribed exercises and health data.
- Technician: Responsible for setting up the device (e.g. assembling the sensors after disinfection), for maintaining the device (e.g. software or sensor update) as well as troubleshooting (e.g. calibration and communication of sensors).

5.5. Functional Overview

The interface is structured into three primary views that dictate available features: Maintenance, Management & Patient view:

- Maintenance View (Technician Only): Provides access to device settings, maintenance, calibration, and game management. Technicians ensure optimal system performance, perform necessary calibrations, and manage game content.
- Management View (Clinician Only): Enables patient management, exercise studio, and data management. Clinicians configure patient data, customize exercise plans, and handle medical records while ensuring compliance with treatment protocols.
- Patient View (Clinician & Patient with distinct access levels): Grants patients access to their prescribed exercises, therapeutic games, health status, and dashboard. Simultaneously, clinicians can review prescription plans, patient history, manual exams, and customizations. This structured access ensures that patients interact only with their assigned treatment programs, while clinicians retain control over medical decisions and session reviews, maintaining data security and integrity.

This structured approach ensures that clinicians retain full control over patient management and patients engage only with their prescribed therapy, enhancing security, usability, and compliance within a clinical environment. Moreover, technicians can maintain and fix any potential issues without interfering with the clinician and patient usage.

5.6. Testing, verification, and validation

This document establishes critical product specifications, subsystems, use case scenarios, and sub scenarios. This information will be used to design a testing strategy to ensure compliance with predefined standards and specifications. Based on this document, a testing methodology and test plan will be developed in task T6.2 to demonstrate that the ThrombUS+ system and its subsystems meet the requirements specified in T2.3 and T6.1, as well as the relevant regulations and standards analyzed in T2.2. Task T6.2 will define a general process for testing, documenting test evidence, and managing test failure processes, including feedback on the overall design of the ThrombUS+ system. Testing will focus on the integrated beta prototype while also addressing individual modules of the alpha prototype. The testing plan will outline the types of tests, descriptions of specific test environments, responsibilities for each test, required equipment or instruments, ergonomic assessments, and other organizational requirements.

5.7. Potential ThrombUS+ system improvements and extensions

There are several avenues for improving the ThrombUS+ system development process, mitigating risks, and exploring potential research directions:

Model-based methodology (MBM) for embedded systems design. MBM enhances abstraction and system understanding by allowing designers to create high-level models, making it easier to visualize and verify

system behavior before implementation. This methodology supports early verification and validation through simulation, reducing the need for costly iterations later in development. It also enables automatic code generation, minimizing human errors and speeding up development. In addition, MBM facilitates rapid prototyping, optimization, and performance tuning, which is important for resource-constrained embedded systems. It is recommended that developers of the ThrombUS+ system modules would make use of modern tools for MBM such as Quantum Leap's QM™⁷.

Real-time embedded optimization. To achieve faster processing times and lower power consumption, it is worth investigating optimized firmware and real-time operating system (RTOS) support. Utilizing event-driven architectures and hierarchical state machines (HSMs) through tools like Quantum Leap's QM™, the system can better manage computational loads and ensure efficient multitasking for ultrasound data and biosignal acquisition, processing, feature extraction, inference, and decision-making.

Possible risk mitigation. ThrombUS+ is a highly innovative system. Key innovations include operator-independent compression ultrasound scanning for DVT detection, which could replace manual monitoring. The feasibility of this method depends on vein visibility during scans, particularly in supine patients, with potential solutions involving automatic calf compression and Doppler ultrasound monitoring. Hydrogel disposable pads are suggested to address issues related to drying ultrasound gel. In addition, EIM and LRM-based VOP will enable automated DVT monitoring while sharing the WMA across modalities. Investigational studies are needed to determine the optimal patient and sensor positioning. Exploring passive monitoring methods through mechanical or electrical stimulation may further enhance venous flow.

Future enhancements of the ThrombUS+ system will focus on refining signal processing algorithms and AI models to improve the accuracy and reliability of DVT detection. Advanced machine learning techniques, such as deep learning-based and biophysics-guided image segmentation and feature extraction, could enhance thrombus detection and characterization by learning complex patterns in ultrasound data. Operator-independent monitoring in both modalities, CDUS and EIM-based VOP, could be achieved by analyzing changes in the extracted features or by applying machine learning methods for anomaly detection.

Possible extension to telemonitoring. A possible extension of the ThrombUS+ system is its integration with telemonitoring capabilities, allowing real-time remote assessment of monitored physiological parameters. As described in Chapter 4, the system is designed to operate autonomously, detecting anomalies and providing alerts when necessary. By enabling telemonitoring, the system could facilitate continuous monitoring by healthcare professionals, improving early intervention and patient management.

⁷ Quantum Leaps' QP™ real-time embedded frameworks (RTEFs) and the tools for embedded systems, <https://www.state-machine.com/>